

MODELING PROVABILITY AND EVALUATION OF SOME LARGE CARDINALS IN THE OBSERVER FRAMEWORK (OBF)

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ABSTRACT. The axioms of OBF are compared with ZFC and logical spaces are analyzed within an environment where large cardinals, including Non-Measurable Cardinals exist and where they can be analyzed. The Provability Status Function τ is evaluated against , Non-Measurable Cardinals, which are characterized by their absence of a non-trivial, κ -complete, 2-valued measure even with their inherent undefinability and self-embedding properties. In order to measure how accurately it reflects the status of these cardinals within OBF. For an added exercise ultimate L is evaluated for existence and constructability within OBF.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The main analysis of provability is determined by the **Provability Status Function** τ , which numerates the provability of propositions within various logical systems of varying cardinality. By assigning distinct weights to propositions based on their provability status—provable p and $\neg p$, undecidable, or undefinable— τ allows for the measurement of provability across different sets of propositions. The **Total Mass of Provability** $\zeta(A)$, is defined as:

$$\zeta(A) = \sum_{(S_\kappa, p_\alpha) \in A} \tau(S_\kappa, p_\alpha)$$

where A is some set of propositions evaluated within some logical system S_κ associated with a cardinal length κ .

The axioms of OBF are compared with ZFC and logical spaces are analyzed within an environment where large cardinals, including Non-Measurable Cardinals exist and where they can be analyzed. The Provability Status Function τ is evaluated against , Non-Measurable Cardinals, which are characterized by their absence of a non-trivial, κ -complete, 2-valued measure even with their inherent undefinability and self-embedding properties. In order to measure how accurately it reflects the status of these cardinals within OBF.

The **Transformation Property**, states the invariance of the Total Mass of Provability ζ under elementary embeddings associated with the Non-Measurable Cardinals. Formally, if $e : V \rightarrow V$ is an elementary embedding with critical point κ , then for any set of propositions $A \subseteq X$:

$$\zeta(e(A)) = \zeta(A)$$

2. PRELIMINARIES

Definition 2.1 (Observer Components). • **Logical Spaces** $\mathcal{M}$: A sequence of mathematical spaces M_n , each associated with an Observer.

Note: Logical Spaces are a subset of the Space of Propositions P

- **Observer Set** $\mathcal{O}$: A set of mathematical entities O_n that evaluate propositions within their respective Logical Spaces M_n .
- **Evaluation Function** $\mathcal{E}$: Determines the truth value of propositions within Logical Spaces:

$$\mathcal{E} : \mathcal{S} \times \mathcal{M} \rightarrow \{\text{True, False}\}$$

- **Provability Measure** μ : A function that assigns weights to propositions based on their provability status within various logical systems:

$$\mu : \mathcal{F} \rightarrow [0, \infty)$$

Defined for any $A \in \mathcal{F}$ by

$$\mu(A) = \sum_{(s,p) \in A} \chi(s,p),$$

where

$$\chi(s,p) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if logical system } s \text{ proves } p, \\ 2, & \text{if logical system } s \text{ proves } \neg p, \\ 3, & \text{if } p \text{ is undecidable in } s, \\ 0, & \text{if } (s,p) \text{ is not in consideration.} \end{cases}$$

Note: The measure μ combines propositions and logical systems, reflecting their provability status. The measure can be thought of as a function of the Observer.

Definition 2.2 (Hyper-Large Cardinals). • **Inaccessible Cardinal**: A cardinal κ that is uncountable, regular, and a strong limit cardinal.

- **Mahlo Cardinal**: A cardinal κ such that the set of regular cardinals less than κ is stationary in κ .
- **Extendible Cardinal**: A cardinal κ is **extendible** if for every ordinal $\lambda > \kappa$, there exists an embedding $r : V \rightarrow M$ with a critical point κ such that:

- (1) **Properties of M** .
- (2) When $x \in M$ and $y \in x$, then $y \in M$.
- (3) When $x \in M$, then $x \subseteq M$.
- (4) **Reflection**: $r(\kappa) > \lambda$.

– **Reasoning**: This rule maps the image of κ under the embedding function r surpasses the ordinal λ . This ensures that the embedding function applies larger than any given λ .

- (5) **Containment of V_λ** : $V_\lambda \subseteq M$.

– **Reasoning**: The ordinal λ -th level of the hierarchy V_λ is contained within the properties of M stated above. This ensures that the embedding function r maps κ larger than λ and structures up to λ are fully mapped within M . This ensures the extendibility of κ by guaranteeing that large portions of the Space are preserved and accurately reflected within M .

*Extendible cardinals are large cardinals, that have the property of reflection.
As a result larger Observers can be mapped onto smaller Logical Spaces and
or observers.*

2.1. Axioms.

Axiom 2.1 (Axiom of Observer Existence). *For every reference space $M_n \in \mathcal{M}$, there exists an observer $O_n \in \mathcal{O}$ such that O_n can perceive and evaluate propositions within M_n .*

Axiom 2.2 (Axiom of the Reference Space). ***Existence and Uniqueness of Reference Spaces:***

$$\forall S_n \in \mathcal{S}, \exists! M_n \in \mathcal{M} \text{ such that } \mathcal{E}(S_n, M_n) = \text{True}$$

Axiom 2.3 (Axiom of Observer Hierarchy Consistency). *For every pair of observers $O_i, O_j \in \mathcal{O}$, if O_i is a subordinate observer to O_j , then the evaluation capabilities of O_i are contained within those of O_j :*

$$\mathcal{E}(S_i, M_i) \subseteq \mathcal{E}(S_j, M_j)$$

Axiom 2.4 (Axiom of Non-Redundancy). *No two distinct observers in $\mathcal{O}$ share the same reference space. Formally:*

$$\forall O_i, O_j \in \mathcal{O}, \quad M_i = M_j \implies O_i = O_j$$

Axiom 2.5 (Axiom of Referential Consistency). *The evaluation of propositions respects Referential ordering. For any logical system S_n and Reference instances $t_m, t_k \in \mathbb{T}$ with $t_m < t_k$:*

$$\mathcal{E}(S_n, M_{t_m}) \text{ is evaluated before } \mathcal{E}(S_n, M_{t_k})$$

Note: Depending on the context Referential can also be termed as Temporal

Axiom 2.6 (Axiom of Comprehensive Coverage). *The collective observation sets of all observers cover the entire proposition space P :*

$$\bigcup_{O_n \in \mathcal{O}} E_n = P$$

Axiom 2.7 (Axiom of Limit Observer Dominance). *The limit observer O_∞ encompasses the evaluation capabilities of all other observers:*

$$\forall O_n \in \mathcal{O}, \quad \mathcal{E}(O_n) \subseteq \mathcal{E}(O_\infty)$$

Axiom 2.8 (Axiom of the Logical Space). *Logical Spaces are organized into an infinite, sequentially alternating sequence of Positive and Negative Logical Spaces. For each natural number $n \in \mathbb{N}$, the n -th Logical Space M_n is defined as follows:*

M_n is a Positive Logical Space $\iff n$ is odd

M_n is a Negative Logical Space $\iff n$ is even

- **Positive Logical Spaces (P):** *The spaces where all standard, non-meta, and non-self-referential statements initially reside. Specifically, unless stated otherwise every statement begins its evaluation in M_1 (P).*
- **Negative Logical Spaces (N):** *The spaces where the evaluation of results, proofs, or subsequent statements that are identified as meta- or self-referential, occurs. When a statement S is determined to be meta- or self-referential within M_n , its evaluation is **reassigned** to the next Logical Space M_{n+1} .*

2.1.1. Optional Axioms.

Axiom 2.9 (Axiom of Hierarchical Delegation). *For any self-referential proposition $S_n \in \mathcal{S}$, if S_n cannot be consistently evaluated within M_n , then its evaluation is delegated to a higher reference space M_{n+1} .*

Axiom 2.10 (Axiom of Autonomy). *Each observer O_n has the autonomy to extend its associated logical system S_n by introducing new axioms $A'_n \subseteq P$, ensuring that the extended system $S'_n = S_n \cup A'_n$ remains consistent:*

$$S'_n = S_n \cup A'_n \quad \text{and} \quad \text{Consistency}(S'_n)$$

Axiom 2.11 (Axiom of Arbitration). *When multiple observers provide conflicting evaluations for the same proposition within distinct reference spaces, the limit observer O_∞ employs an arbitration function $\mathcal{A}$ to determine the final truth value:*

$$\mathcal{E}_\infty(S) = \mathcal{A}(\{\mathcal{E}(O_n, M_n)(S) \mid O_n \in \mathcal{O}\})$$

where $\mathcal{A}$ is a predefined logical operation or system (e.g., majority vote, consensus, hierarchical priority) that resolves the set of truth values into a single, consistent truth value for S . Note: The value of the logical system depends on context

Axiom 2.12 (Axiom of Alternating Truth Consistency). *The truth values of sequential and independent propositions alternate consistently across distinct logical systems and reference spaces:*

$$\forall S_n, S_m \in \mathcal{S}, \quad \text{Independent}(S_n, S_m) \implies T(S_n, t_n) = \neg T(S_m, t_m)$$

Note: Alternating refers to the consistent inversion of truth values across independent propositions evaluated within distinct logical systems and reference spaces from the seed space.

2.2. Selected Observer Axioms.

Axiom 2.13 (Axiom of Observer Existence). *For every Logical Space $M_n \in \mathcal{M}$, there exists an Observer $O_n \in \mathcal{O}$ that evaluates propositions within M_n .*

Axiom 2.14 (Axiom of the Reference Space). *Each statement S_n is evaluated within a unique Logical Space M_n :*

$$\forall S_n \in \mathcal{S}, \quad \exists! M_n \in \mathcal{M} \text{ such that } \mathcal{E}(S_n, M_n) \in \{\text{True}, \text{False}\}$$

Axiom 2.15 (Axiom of Observer Hierarchy Consistency). *If Observer O_i is subordinate to Observer O_j , then:*

$$\mathcal{E}(S_i, M_i) \subseteq \mathcal{E}(S_j, M_j)$$

Axiom 2.16 (Axiom of Non-Redundancy). *No two distinct Observers share the same Logical Space:*

$$\forall O_i, O_j \in \mathcal{O}, \quad M_i = M_j \implies O_i = O_j$$

3. LARGE OBSERVABLE CARDINALS: IE. MAHLO CARDINALS

3.1. Definitions.

Definition 3.1 (Regular Cardinal). A cardinal κ is **regular** if it is equal to its cofinality; meaning, there is no smaller cardinality of an unbounded subset whose supremum is κ .

Definition 3.2 (Stationary Set). A subset S of a limit ordinal λ is **stationary** in λ if S intersects every closed unbounded subset of λ .

Definition 3.3 (Mahlo Cardinal). A cardinal κ is a **Mahlo cardinal** if:

- (1) κ is uncountable and regular.
- (2) The set of regular cardinals less than κ is stationary in κ .

3.2. Logical Spaces and Observers.

Definition 3.4 (Logical Space and Observer). For each cardinal n :

- **Logical Space** M_n : Can be defined as a mathematical structure containing all sets of cardinality less than or equal to n .
- **Observer** O_n : An entity associated with M_n that evaluates propositions within M_n .

3.3. Set Cardinalities and Logical Spaces. Sets and their cardinalities, along with their associated Logical Space and Observer:

$$\begin{aligned}
 |\emptyset| &= 0, & M_0, & O_0 \\
 |\{0\}| &= 1, & M_1, & O_1 \\
 |\{0, 1\}| &= 2, & M_2, & O_2 \\
 |\{0, 1, 2\}| &= 3, & M_3, & O_3 \\
 &\vdots & & \\
 |\{0, 1, \dots, n-1\}| &= n, & M_n, & O_n \\
 &\vdots & & \\
 \text{Up to } \kappa - 1, & & M_{\kappa-1}, & O_{\kappa-1}
 \end{aligned}$$

Where:

- Each M_n corresponds to sets of cardinality less than or equal to n .
- Observer O_n is associated with Logical Space M_n .

3.4. Proof of Existence.

Proof. (1) **Assumption:** Assume there exists a Mahlo cardinal κ .
 (2) **Definition:** Logical Space M_κ are associated with Observer O_κ .
 (3) **Construction of M_κ :** Building M_κ to contain all sets of cardinality less than κ , by adhering to the properties of Mahlo cardinals. Specifically,

consider the sequence:

$$\begin{aligned}
|\emptyset| &= 0, & M_0, & O_0 \\
|\{0\}| &= 1, & M_1, & O_1 \\
|\{0, 1\}| &= 2, & M_2, & O_2 \\
|\{0, 1, 2\}| &= 3, & M_3, & O_3 \\
&\vdots \\
|\{0, 1, \dots, n-1\}| &= n, & M_n, & O_n \\
&\vdots \\
|\{0, 1, \dots, \lambda-1\}| &= \lambda, & M_\lambda, & O_\lambda \\
&\vdots \\
&\text{Up to } \kappa - 1, & M_{\kappa-1}, & O_{\kappa-1}
\end{aligned}$$

Each M_n sets of cardinality less than or equal to n , and is associated with Observer O_n .

- (4) **The Overset of Previous Logical Spaces:** Since κ is uncountable and regular, the union of all M_n for $n < \kappa$ cannot reach κ . Therefore, M_κ includes all Logical Spaces M_n for $n < \kappa$.
- (5) **Extending to $M_{\kappa+1}$:** To contain the cardinality of M_κ and the element κ , Observation defines there exist $M_{\kappa+1}$ with a cardinality $\kappa+1$. An associate Observer $O_{\kappa+1}$ observers propositions within $M_{\kappa+1}$.
- (6) **Axioms in use:**
 - **Axiom of Observer Existence:** For each $n \leq \kappa + 1$, Observer O_n exists for Logical Space M_n by OBF's definition.
 - **Axiom of the Reference Space:** Propositions involving elements of M_n are uniquely evaluated within M_n by O_n , maintaining consistency and avoiding ambiguity.
 - **Axiom of Observer Hierarchy Consistency:** For $n < m \leq \kappa + 1$, There exist an Observer O_n which is subordinate to Observer O_m as a result of the ordering of cardinals.
 - **Axiom of Non-Redundancy:** Each M_n and O_n are unique since each cardinal n is unique.
- (7) **Properties of Mahlo Cardinals:** Since κ is a Mahlo cardinal, the set of regular cardinals less than κ is stationary in κ . This ensures that the hierarchy of Logical Spaces $\{M_n\}_{n < \kappa}$ is inclusive of all necessary cardinalities below κ .
- (8) **Existence within Observation sets:** By construction, M_κ and O_κ exist within the Observer Frame of reference without conflicting with its existing axioms. The system can contain κ naturally.
- (9) **Conclusion:** Mahlo cardinals exist within OBF. The sequence of Logical Spaces and Observers extend naturally to include κ and potentially larger, while maintaining its structure.

□

3.5. Reasoning. By showing the existence of Mahlo cardinals within OBF, large cardinal observers may be used to model and analyze large complex, logical and or mathematical structures.

4. MODELING THE ULTIMATE L WITHIN OBF

4.1. Overview. To demonstrate that **Ultimate L** can be modeled within OBF, larger cardinal Observers will be mapped onto smaller sets within themselves. By using the properties of extendible cardinals and the axioms of OBF.

4.2. Key Concepts.

Definition 4.1 (Extendible Cardinal). A cardinal κ is **extendible** if for every ordinal $\lambda > \kappa$, there exists an embedding $r : V \rightarrow M$ with critical point κ such that:

- (1) $r(\kappa) > \lambda$.
- (2) $V_\lambda \subseteq \text{range}(r)$.

Definition 4.2 (Observers and the Logical Space). For each cardinal κ :

- **Logical Space** M_κ : sets of cardinality less than κ .
- **Observer** O_κ : Evaluates propositions within M_κ .

4.3. Proof.

Proof. (1) **Assumption:** Let δ be an extendible cardinal within observation. Such a cardinal can exist by assumption.

(2) **Construction of Logical Spaces and Observers:**

- For each $n < \delta$, there can be defined a Logical Space M_n and Observer O_n as usual.
- By Defining M_δ it must sets of cardinality less than δ .
- Associate an Observer O_δ with M_δ .

(3) **Mapping Larger Observers onto Smaller Sets:**

- Since δ is extendible, there exists an embedding function $r : V \rightarrow M$ with a critical point δ and $r(\delta) > \delta$.
- The embedding function r maps sets and structures in V to larger ones while preserving all set-theoretic truths.
- For example, r maps M_δ to $M_{r(\delta)}$ and O_δ to $O_{r(\delta)}$.

(4) **Reflection of Lower Observers into Higher Ones:**

- For each $n < \delta$, O_n and M_n are included in M_δ .
- The embeddings of r ensures that the images of these Observers and Logical Spaces are included in $M_{r(\delta)}$.
- This mapping reflects the properties of lower Observers into the higher-level Observer $O_{r(\delta)}$.

(5) **Establishing Ultimate L within OBF:**

- Define $M_{\text{Ultimate L}} := M_\delta$.
- Associate $O_{\text{Ultimate L}} := O_\delta$.
- Since M_δ sets of cardinality less than δ , and δ is extendible, M_δ reflects all smaller structures within itself.

(6) **Observer Axioms used:**

- (a) **Axiom of Observer Existence:** Observers O_n exist for all $n \leq \delta$.
- (b) **Axiom of the Reference Space:** Each Observer O_n evaluates propositions within its Logical Space M_n .

(c) **Axiom of Observer Hierarchy Consistency:** For $n < m \leq \delta$, Observer O_n is subordinate to O_m .

(d) **Axiom of Non-Redundancy:** Each M_n and O_n are unique to their cardinalities.

(7) **Conclusion:**

- By mapping larger cardinal Observers onto smaller sets within themselves via the extendibility of δ , we have established that O_δ effectively encompasses both lower and higher Observers.
- This construction models Ultimate L within OBF, as M_δ sets and structures necessary for Ultimate L to function.
- The Observer axioms are maintained throughout this construction. $\square$

4.4. Reasoning.

- **Existence of Ultimate L:** The proof demonstrates that Ultimate L exists within OBF as M_δ with Observer O_δ .
- **Reflection:** Lower Observers are reflected into higher Observers, showcasing OBF's ability to handle infinite hierarchies.
- **Consistency with Given Axioms:** The mapping preserves all axioms of the Observer.

4.5. **Addendum. Ultimate L Within OBF,** we can model a Ultimate L by mapping larger cardinal Observers onto smaller sets within themselves, leveraging the properties of extendible cardinals.

4.5.1. *Mapping Function.* Consider the following hierarchy of Observers and Logical Spaces:

$$\begin{aligned}
 |\emptyset| &= 0, & M_0, & O_0 \\
 |\{0\}| &= 1, & M_1, & O_1 \\
 |\{0, 1\}| &= 2, & M_2, & O_2 \\
 &\vdots & & \\
 |\{0, 1, \dots, n-1\}| &= n, & M_n, & O_n \\
 &\vdots & & \\
 |\{0, 1, \dots, \kappa-1\}| &= \kappa, & M_\kappa, & O_\kappa \\
 &\vdots & &
 \end{aligned}$$

At larger cardinalities, specifically at extendible cardinals, The following can be observed:

- The Observer O_κ associated with an extendible cardinal κ can be **mapped** onto smaller sets within itself via an embedding function.
- The mapping preserves the structure and properties of the Observer, effectively allowing O_κ to **reflect** aspects of smaller Observers O_n for $n < \kappa$.

4.6. **Proof dialogue.**

(1) **Reflecting Lower Observers onto Higher Ones:**

- The mapping shows that lower finite propositional Observers O_n for $n < \delta$ can be reflected into higher-level Observers O_δ .
- This reflection maintains the axioms of the Observer, such as the Axiom of Observer Hierarchy Consistency and the Axiom of Non-Redundancy.

(2) **Establishing O_δ as Ultimate L's Observer:**

- By using the extendibility of δ , Observer O_δ can capture the properties required for a Ultimate L.
- O_δ evaluates propositions within M_δ that include all sets constructible up to δ , mirroring the constructibility within an Ultimate L.

(3) **Maintaining Observer Axioms:**

- The mappings and embedding functions preserve the Axiom of Observer Existence, since each mapped Observer exists within OBF.
- The Axiom of the Reference Space is maintained, since propositions are uniquely evaluated within their respective Logical Spaces.
- The Axiom of Observer Hierarchy's Consistency is maintained through the ordering of cardinals and the embeddings.
- The Axiom of Non-Redundancy maintained, since each Observer and Logical Space pair remains unique.

(4) **Conclusion:** By mapping larger cardinal Observers onto smaller sets within themselves and using extendible cardinals, We can construct an Observer O_δ that serves as the Observer for Ultimate L. This shows that Ultimate L exists within the Observer Frame, while satisfying the required axioms and properties.

5. ILLUSTRATIVE EXAMPLE OF EMBEDDINGS IN OBF

5.1. **Finite Mapping example.** To gain an intuition of how embeddings operate within OBF, we can consider a simplified finite example. Although finite examples cannot capture the full complexity of a cardinal embedding, they can serve as a tool for illustrating the concept.

5.1.1. *The Finite Sequence.* Consider the following finite sequence of elements representing Observers and Logical Spaces:

$$\{1, 2, 3, 4, 5\}$$

Here, each number corresponds to a distinct Observer and its associated Logical Space:

- **1:** Observer O_1 evaluates Logical Space M_1
- **2:** Observer O_2 evaluates Logical Space M_2
- **3:** Observer O_3 evaluates Logical Space M_3 (Critical Point)
- **4:** Observer O_4 evaluates Logical Space M_4
- **5:** Observer O_5 evaluates Logical Space M_5

5.1.2. *Mapping Observers via embeddings.* We can define an embedding r that will map larger Observers to smaller Logical Spaces, with the Observer O_3 serving as the critical point. The mapping is as follows:

Original Observer	Mapped Logical Space
O_5	M_1
O_4	M_2
O_3	M_5
O_2	(Fixed)
O_1	(Fixed)

The critical point is O_3 , meaning that Observers with indices below 3 will remain fixed, while those above are mapped to lower indices.

5.1.3. Visualization of the Mapping.

Observer	Logical Space	Mapping via r
O_1	M_1	$O_1 \mapsto M_1$ (Fixed)
O_2	M_2	$O_2 \mapsto M_2$ (Fixed)
O_3	M_3	$O_3 \mapsto M_5$ (Critical Point)
O_4	M_4	$O_4 \mapsto M_2$
O_5	M_5	$O_5 \mapsto M_1$

This table summarizes how each Observer is mapped to a Logical Space using the embedding r .

5.2. Interpreting $r(\kappa) > \lambda$ in the Finite Example. In the context of large cardinals and embeddings, the condition $r(\kappa) > \lambda$ will ensure that the image of the critical point κ under the embedding function r exceeds any ordinal λ greater than κ . Translating this to our finite example:

- **Critical Point:** $\kappa = 3$ (Observer O_3 evaluating M_3)
- **Ordinal λ :** Choose $\lambda = 4$
- **Embedding Condition:** $r(\kappa) = r(3) = 5 > 4 = \lambda$

Therefore, the mapping will satisfy $r(\kappa) > \lambda$.

5.2.1. Understanding $r(\kappa) \cdot \lambda$. In set theory, the notation $r(\kappa)(\lambda)$ will usually refer to the image of λ under the embedding r . Translating this into our finite example:

- $r(\kappa)$: $r(3) = 5$
- $r(\kappa)(\lambda)$: $r(5) = 1$

Therefore, $r(\kappa)(\lambda) = 1$.

5.3. Analysis of the Finite Example.

5.3.1. Reflection of Observers. - **Lower Observers Fixed:** Observers O_1 and O_2 will remain fixed, similar to how elements below the critical point in higher cardinals are unaffected by the embedding functions.

- **Higher Observers Mapped Down:** Observers O_4 and O_5 are mapped to lower Logical Spaces M_2 and M_1 , respectively. This reflects the embedding's ability to reflect larger Observers onto smaller Logical Spaces while preserving the critical structure at O_3 .

5.3.2. Critical Point and Supremacy. - **Critical Point O_3 :** Serves as the hinge around which the embedding function operates. It remains fixed in this finite example, mirroring the behavior of κ in larger cardinals.

- **Supremacy $r(\kappa) > \lambda$:** The mapping $r(3) = 5 > 4 = \lambda$ satisfies the condition, demonstrating that the embedding extends larger than the chosen λ .

5.3.3. *Containment* $V_\lambda \subseteq M$. In set theory, $V_\lambda \subseteq M$ ensures that the structure up to λ is fully embedded within M . Translating to our finite example:

- $V_4 \subseteq M$: Since $\lambda = 4$, V_4 corresponds to the sequence $\{1, 2, 3, 4\}$. Under the embedding r , $M = \{1, 2, 5\}$, which does not fully contain V_4 .

Result: This result shows the limitation of finite examples. In actual higher cardinal embeddings, $V_\lambda \subseteq M$ ensures comprehensive containment, which is challenging to represent accurately within a finite example.

5.4. **Limitations of a Finite example.** While the finite example provides valuable intuition, it can have inherent limitations:

- **Infinite vs. Finite Structures:** Set-theoretic embedding functions operate on infinite hierarchies, preserving intricate structural properties that finite sequences cannot simulate easily.
- **Transitivity and Closure:** The finite example cannot fully capture the transitivity and closure conditions required in set-theoretic models.
- **Ordinal Arithmetic:** Concepts like V_λ and their containment within M are inherently infinite and cannot be accurately depicted with finite elements.

6. INFINITE CARDINAL EXAMPLE USING δ

6.1. **Introduction.** With the finite mapping example in mind, consider an infinite cardinal example using the cardinal δ to illustrate the concepts of an elementary embeddings and critical points in the context of large cardinals. This example provides a deeper understanding of how these concepts operate within infinite structures.

6.2. **Setting Up the Infinite Example.** Let δ be an uncountable regular cardinal. For the purposes of this example, consider δ to be a **measurable cardinal**, which is a type of large cardinal with properties related to an elementary embeddings.

6.2.1. *Definitions.*

- **Measurable Cardinal:** A cardinal δ is measurable if there exists a non-trivial, δ -additive ultrafilter U oversetting δ that is *non-principal*. Equivalently, there exists a non-trivial elementary embedding $r : V \rightarrow M$ with critical point δ , where M is a transitive class, $r(\delta) > \delta$, and $M \supseteq V$.
- **Critical Point δ :** The smallest ordinal moved by the embedding r , i.e., for all $\alpha < \delta$, $r(\alpha) = \alpha$, but $r(\delta) > \delta$.
- **Ultrapower Construction:** The model M can be obtained as the ultrapower of V by the ultrafilter U , denoted as $M = \text{Ult}(V, U)$.

6.3. **Constructing the Elementary Embedding.**

6.3.1. *Ultrafilter U Over δ .* Consider an ultrafilter U over δ with the following properties:

- (1) U is non-principal, meaning it is not generated by a single element of δ .
- (2) U is δ -complete, i.e., it is closed under intersections of fewer than δ sets.

6.3.2. *Ultrapower Model M .* Using U , we can construct the ultrapower of V :

$$M = \text{Ult}(V, U)$$

The elementary embedding $r : V \rightarrow M$ is defined by:

$$r(x) = [f_x]_U$$

where $f_x : \delta \rightarrow V$ is the constant function with value x , and $[f_x]_U$ denotes the equivalence class of f_x under the ultrafilter U .

6.3.3. *Properties of the Embedding r .* The embedding function r has the following properties:

- (1) **Critical Point:** $\text{crit}(r) = \delta$, meaning $r(\alpha) = \alpha$ for all $\alpha < \delta$, and $r(\delta) > \delta$.
- (2) **Elementarity:** For any formula $\phi(x_1, \dots, x_n)$ and elements $a_1, \dots, a_n \in V$:

$$V \models \phi(a_1, \dots, a_n) \iff M \models \phi(r(a_1), \dots, r(a_n))$$

- (3) **Transitivity of M :** M is a transitive class, meaning if $x \in y$ and $y \in M$, then $x \in M$.

6.4. Interpretation within OBF.

6.4.1. *Observers and Logical Spaces.* In this infinite example, we can think of:

- **Observers:** as elements of V up to V_δ .
- **Logical Spaces:** The structures or sets that the Observers evaluate, also elements of V up to V_δ .

The elementary embedding r maps Observers and Logical Spaces from V into the transitive class M , preserving all first-order properties.

6.4.2. *Critical Point and Mapping.* - **Critical Point δ :** Observers and Logical Spaces that correspond to ordinals less than δ will remain fixed under r . - **Mapping larger than δ :** For ordinals $\alpha \geq \delta$, $r(\alpha) > \alpha$, meaning that Observers and Logical Spaces at levels larger than δ are moved and or stretched by the embedding function.

6.4.3. *Containment of V_δ .* The embedding function r satisfies:

$$V_\delta \subseteq M$$

This means that all sets and structures up to level δ are contained within M , therefore the embedding captures the entire universe up to δ .

6.5. **Visualization of the Embedding.** Since it's challenging to visualize infinite structures, we can understand that:

- **Elements Below δ :** Will remain unchanged under r .
- **Element δ :** Critical point mapped to $r(\delta) > \delta$.
- **Elements Above δ :** Mapped further up, with their positions shifted by the embedding.

6.6. **Implications for OBF.** The infinite cardinal example using δ illustrates how large cardinals enable the mapping of entire mathematical universes up to a certain level within a larger structure while preserving the properties of Observers and Logical Spaces. This reflects the extendibility and reflection properties critical for constructing models like an Ultimate L within OBF.

6.7. Conclusion. By examining an infinite cardinal example with δ , we can gain an understanding of how elementary embeddings and critical points function in the infinite settings.

7. PROVABILITY MEASURES WITHIN OBF

7.1. Introduction. To measure the provability of propositions across various logical systems requires a function that can provide some approach to manage and evaluate these propositions. While Logical Spaces represent the Cartesian product between logical systems and propositions and Observers represent an interpretive entity in order to systematically assess the provability of propositions within OBF, A trans-observable function **Provability Measure** assigns weights to propositions based on their provability status across different logical systems, ranging from finite to infinite cardinals of varying strengths, densities, and properties, including advanced systems beyond current models.

7.2. Definition of the Provability Measure.

Definition 7.1 (Provability Measure). A **Provability Measure** μ is a function that assigns non-negative weights to sets of propositions based on their provability status within various logical systems. Formally, it is defined as:

$$\mu : \mathcal{F} \rightarrow [0, \infty)$$

where $\mathcal{F}$ is the collection of all relevant subsets of propositions.

For any set $A \in \mathcal{F}$, the measure $\mu(A)$ is given by:

$$\mu(A) = \sum_{(s,p) \in A} \chi(s,p),$$

where s represents a logical system ie(inference rules, axioms, etc.) and p represents a proposition. The function $\chi(s,p)$ assigns weights based on the provability status of p within s :

$$\chi(s,p) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if logical system } s \text{ proves } p, \\ 2, & \text{if logical system } s \text{ proves } \neg p, \\ 3, & \text{if } p \text{ is undecidable in } s, \\ 0, & \text{if } (s,p) \text{ is not in consideration or relatively empty.} \end{cases}$$

7.3. Interpretation of the Provability Measure. The provability measure μ can serve as a quantitative tool to evaluate the status of propositions across different logical systems. Here's how to interpret the assigned weights:

- **Weight 1:** Indicates that the proposition p is *provable* (true) within the given logical system s .
- **Weight 2:** Indicates that the proposition p is *provably false* (i.e., $\neg p$ is provable) within the given logical system s .
- **Weight 3:** indicates that the proposition p is *undecidable* within the given logical system s ; neither p nor $\neg p$ can be proven within s .
- **Weight 0:** Implies that the pair (s,p) is *not relevant* or *not under consideration* within the current evaluation.

7.4. Application to Finite and Infinite Logical Systems. When it comes to a wide variety of logical systems, from finite to infinite cardinals. The provability measure μ can be applied uniformly across these systems of propositions irrespective of the referenced s logical strength.

7.4.1. *Finite Logical Systems.* Consider a finite logical system S_n with a finite number of propositions. In this context:

- Each proposition p in S_n can be evaluated for provability, falsifiability, or undecidability.
- The measure μ will sum these evaluations to provide an overall weight for any subset of propositions A .

Example:

Let S_1 be a simple propositional logic system with propositions $\{p, q, r\}$.

$$A = \{(S_1, p), (S_1, q), (S_1, r)\}$$

Assume:

$$\begin{aligned}\chi(S_1, p) &= 1 \quad (S_1 \text{ proves } p) \\ \chi(S_1, q) &= 3 \quad (q \text{ is undecidable in } S_1) \\ \chi(S_1, r) &= 2 \quad (S_1 \text{ proves } \neg r)\end{aligned}$$

Then:

$$\mu(A) = 1 + 3 + 2 = 6$$

7.4.2. *Infinite Logical Systems.* For infinite logical systems, like those associated with large cardinals such as Mhalo Cardinals.

Example:

Let S_κ be a logical system associated with some Large Cardinal κ . Consider a set of propositions in set $A = \{(S_\kappa, p_\alpha) \mid \alpha < \lambda\}$, where λ is some ordinal related to κ .

Assume:

$$\chi(S_\kappa, p_\alpha) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } p_\alpha \text{ is provable in } S_\kappa, \\ 2, & \text{if } \neg p_\alpha \text{ is provable in } S_\kappa, \\ 3, & \text{if } p_\alpha \text{ is undecidable in } S_\kappa. \end{cases}$$

Given the potential vastness of S_κ , $\mu(A)$ will sum these evaluations across a potentially transfinite number of propositions.

7.5. Impact of Cardinality on μ . The measure μ numerical value can potentially exceed the **cardinality** of a set of propositions. This relationship between the cardinality of A and $\mu(A)$ is influenced by the cardinality of λ relative to κ .

- **Finite λ :** If λ is finite, $\mu(A)$ is simply the sum of finite weights, providing a direct measure of provability within S_κ .
- **Infinite λ :** For some infinite ordinal λ , like those related to some large cardinals κ , $\mu(A)$ sums the weights over an unbounded or highly structured set of propositions. This numerical sum can result in $\mu(A)$ attaining a numerical value that exceed the original sets cardinality A , especially when A approaches the size of $\mathcal{P}(V)$ if given the appropriate logical system to do so.

Remark 7.1. Given the cardinality of $|S| = 2^{2^{\aleph_0}}$ and $|P| = 2^{\aleph_0}$, the space X of all pairs (S_κ, p_α) is extraordinarily large. As a result, $\mu(A)$ can map sets with immense cardinalities to numerical values that encapsulate the collective provability status of their contained propositions.

7.6. Measure within (OBF). Within OBF, the provability measure μ assesses propositions across the structure of Observers and Logical Spaces. Here's how μ integrates with OBF:

- (1) **Observer Hierarchy:** Each Observer O_n observes some Logical Space M_n , that corresponds to a specific logical system S_n . The provability measure μ is applied within each M_n to evaluate propositions based on S_n 's capability.
- (2) **Logical Spaces:** Logical Spaces represent distinct environments where different logical systems can operate. The provability measure makes it possible to read each Logical Space and independently assess the status of propositions.
- (3) **Scalability:** OBF's properties allow μ to scale within finite and or various infinite logical systems, ensuring definability across diverse logical strengths.
- (4) **Accommodation of Large or exotic Cardinals:** For logical systems associated with large or potentially unseen exotic cardinals, μ can reflect advanced embedding functional properties and provability statuses within these systems.

7.7. Properties of the Provability Measure.

- **Quantitative Analysis:** By assigning numerical weights, μ can provide a means to compare and analyze the provability of propositions across different logical systems.
- **Layered Analysis:** OBF's structure, combined with μ , allows for layered analysis of definable and undefinable propositions, where higher Observers can assess propositions with greater logical strength and complexity.

7.8. Provability Measure as a Filter and Ultrafilter.

Definition 7.2 (Provability Filter). Given the Provability Measure $\mu : \mathcal{F} \rightarrow [0, \infty)$, define the Provability Filter $\mathcal{F}_\mu$ as:

$$\mathcal{F}_\mu = \{A \subseteq \mathcal{F} \mid \mu(A) \geq k\}$$

for a chosen threshold $k \in \mathbb{N}$.

Proposition 7.1 (Filter Properties). $\mathcal{F}_\mu$ is a filter on $\mathcal{F}$ provided that:

- (1) $\mathcal{F}_\mu$ is non-empty.
- (2) If $A, B \in \mathcal{F}_\mu$, then $A \cap B \in \mathcal{F}_\mu$.
- (3) If $A \in \mathcal{F}_\mu$ and $A \subseteq B \subseteq \mathcal{F}$, then $B \in \mathcal{F}_\mu$.

Proof. (1) Non-Emptiness: Assume there exists at least one $A \subseteq \mathcal{F}$ such that $\mu(A) \geq k$. Thus, $\mathcal{F}_\mu$ is non-empty.

- (2) Closure Under Intersection: For $A, B \in \mathcal{F}_\mu$,

$$\mu(A \cap B) = \sum_{(s,p) \in A \cap B} \chi(s,p) \geq \mu(A) + \mu(B) - \mu(A \cup B)$$

Choose k such that $\mu(A \cap B) \geq k$, ensuring $A \cap B \in \mathcal{F}_\mu$.

- (3) Upward Closure: If $A \in \mathcal{F}_\mu$ and $A \subseteq B \subseteq \mathcal{F}$, then $\mu(B) \geq \mu(A) \geq k$, hence $B \in \mathcal{F}_\mu$. □

8. THE PROVABILITY MEASURE AND LARGE CARDINALS WITHIN OBF

8.1. Introduction. Within OBF, the **Provability Measure** μ measures and indicates the provability of propositions across a spectra of logical systems. The interaction between μ and logical systems associated with large cardinals influence the measure in exotic ways. furthermore, addressing and handling of **undefinable propositions** requires the measure's applicability to extend to any potential context.

8.2. Logical Systems and Large Cardinals.

Definition 8.1 (Logical System S_κ). Let κ be some **Large Cardinal**. Logical System S_κ is defined as a formal system that incorporates axioms, inference rules and proofs pertaining to κ , which enables the derivation of potential propositions within the context of κ 's based on its properties.

Remark 8.1. Logical systems S_κ inherit the strength and or characteristics of their associated large cardinals. For example, if κ is a **measurable cardinal**, S_κ would include axioms related to ultrafilters and embedding functions pertinent to κ . Similarly, for a potential **Exotic Cardinal**, S_κ would account for its unique properties.

8.3. Set of Propositions Indexed by Ordinals.

Definition 8.2 (Set of Propositions A). For a given large cardinal κ , consider the set of propositions A defined as:

$$A = \{(S_\kappa, p_\alpha) \mid \alpha < \lambda\},$$

where λ is some ordinal related to κ , ie(the rank or height of κ).

Example 8.1. Let κ be some **measurable cardinal** and $\lambda = \kappa^+$ (the successor cardinal of κ). Then, A will contain of all pairs (S_κ, p_α) for $\alpha < \kappa^+$, representing propositions that can be formulated and evaluated within S_κ .

8.4. Cardinality and the Provability Measure. The **Provability Measure** μ quantifies the provability of sets of propositions by summing the value assigned by χ .

Definition 8.3 (Cardinal Provability Measure μ). where $\mathcal{F}$ is a family of subsets of X , with X representing all possible pairs (S_κ, p_α) .

For any $A \in \mathcal{F}$,

$$\mu(A) = \sum_{(S_\kappa, p_\alpha) \in A} \chi(S_\kappa, p_\alpha).$$

8.5. Provability Status and Weight Function. In order to address the value of 0 within the provability measure consider the following function.

Definition 8.4 (Provability Status Function τ). Define the **Provability Status Function** τ for each pair (S_κ, p_α) as:

$$\tau(S_\kappa, p_\alpha) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } p_\alpha \text{ is provable in } S_\kappa, \\ 2, & \text{if } \neg p_\alpha \text{ is provable in } S_\kappa, \\ 3, & \text{if } p_\alpha \text{ is undecidable in } S_\kappa, \\ 4, & \text{if } p_\alpha \text{ is undefinable in } S_\kappa. \end{cases}$$

Remark 8.2. The weights assigned by τ represent the provability status of propositions within their respective logical systems similar to the provability measure:

- **Weight 1:** Proposition p_α is provable as true in S_κ .
- **Weight 2:** Proposition p_α is provable as false (i.e., $\neg p_\alpha$ is provable) in S_κ .
- **Weight 3:** Proposition p_α is undecidable in S_κ ; neither p_α nor $\neg p_\alpha$ can be proven within S_κ .
- **Weight 4:** Proposition p_α is undefinable in S_κ ; it cannot be expressed or formulated within the language of S_κ .

8.6. Filter and Ultrafilter Construction Based on τ . To potentially allow for another tool of analysis of Provability, Filters can be assigned to the Function τ by constructing these **filters** or **ultrafilters** we may sort and categorize sets of propositions based on their provability weight.

8.6.1. *Constructing a Provability Filter.*

Definition 8.5 (Provability Filter $\mathcal{F}_\tau$). Given the Provability Status Function τ and a chosen threshold $k \in \{1, 2, 3, 4\}$, define the **Provability Filter** $\mathcal{F}_\tau$ as:

$$\mathcal{F}_\tau = \{A \subseteq X \mid \tau(A) \geq k\}.$$

Remark 8.3. Define the value of k to be one of $k \in \{1, 2, 3, 4\}$, where each value filters subsets based on their provability status. τ is **monotonic**, i.e., for any $A \subseteq B \subseteq X$, $\tau(A) \leq \tau(B)$.

Theorem 8.1 (Filter Properties of $\mathcal{F}_\tau$). *Collection $\mathcal{F}_\tau$ satisfies the properties of a filter on X :*

- (1) **Non-Empty:** *There exists at least one $A \subseteq X$ such that $\tau(A) \geq k$, therefore $\mathcal{F}_\tau$ is non-empty.*
- (2) **Upward Closed:** *If $A \in \mathcal{F}_\tau$ and $A \subseteq B \subseteq X$, then $B \in \mathcal{F}_\tau$ because $\tau(B) \geq \tau(A) \geq k$.*
- (3) **Closed Under Finite Intersection:** *If $A, B \in \mathcal{F}_\tau$, then $A \cap B \in \mathcal{F}_\tau$ provided $\tau(A \cap B) \geq k$. This holds since the intersection of any two subsets in $\mathcal{F}_\tau$ retains a provability status of at least k .*

Proof. (1) **Non-Emptiness:** Assume there exists at least one subset $A \subseteq X$ such that $\tau(A) \geq k$. By definition, $A \in \mathcal{F}_\tau$, ensuring $\mathcal{F}_\tau$ is non-empty.

(2) **Upward Closure:** Let $A \in \mathcal{F}_\tau$ and $A \subseteq B \subseteq X$. Given that τ is monotonic (i.e., $A \subseteq B$ implies $\tau(A) \leq \tau(B)$), and since $\tau(A) \geq k$, it follows that $\tau(B) \geq k$. Therefore, $B \in \mathcal{F}_\tau$.

(3) **Closure Under Finite Intersection:** Given $A, B \in \mathcal{F}_\tau$, we have:

$$\tau(A) \geq k \quad \text{and} \quad \tau(B) \geq k$$

Since τ is monotonic, $A \subseteq A \cup B$ implies:

$$\tau(A) \leq \tau(A \cup B)$$

Similarly:

$$\tau(B) \leq \tau(A \cup B)$$

However, without additive properties, we rely on the design of τ to ensure that:

$$\tau(A \cap B) \geq k$$

This holds because: If $A \cap B$ contains at least one undecidable proposition, $\tau(A \cap B) \geq 3$. If $A \cap B$ contains at least one false provable proposition and no undecidable propositions, $\tau(A \cap B) \geq 2$. If $A \cap B$ contains only true provable propositions, $\tau(A \cap B) = 1$, which is **not** ≥ 2 . However, since $A, B \in \mathcal{F}_\tau$, at least one of them must contain a false or undecidable proposition, ensuring $A \cap B$ retains a sufficient τ -value.

Therefore, $\tau(A \cap B) \geq k$, implying $A \cap B \in \mathcal{F}_\tau$. **Conclusion:** The Closure Under Finite Intersection property holds. $\square$

9. EXAMPLE: NON-ADDITIVE, MONOTONIC τ MAINTAINS FILTER PROPERTIES

To illustrate how a non-additive, monotonic Provability Status Function τ maintains filter properties, consider the following example.

Example Setup. Ground Set X :

$$X = \{(S_\kappa, p_1), (S_\kappa, p_2), (S_\kappa, p_3)\}$$

Here, each element (S_κ, p_i) represents a proposition p_i within a logical system S_κ .

Provability Status Function τ : Can be Defined τ based on the properties of subsets:

$$\tau(A) = \begin{cases} 4, & \text{if } A = \emptyset \text{ (undefinable),} \\ 3, & \text{if } A \text{ contains at least one undecidable proposition,} \\ 2, & \text{if } A \text{ contains at least one provable } \neg p \text{ proposition and no undecidable propositions,} \\ 1, & \text{if } A \text{ contains only provable } p \text{ propositions.} \end{cases}$$

This definition ensures that τ is **monotonic**, which means that adding propositions to a subset can only maintain or increase its τ -value:

$$\text{If } A \subseteq B, \text{ then } \tau(A) \leq \tau(B).$$

Filter Definition: Choose $k = 2$:

$$\mathcal{F}_\tau = \{A \subseteq X \mid \tau(A) \geq 2\}$$

9.1. Identifying Sets in $\mathcal{F}_\tau$.

- **Set A :**

$$A = \{(S_\kappa, p_1)\}, \quad \tau(A) = 1 \notin \mathcal{F}_\tau$$

- **Set B :**

$$B = \{(S_\kappa, p_2)\}, \quad \tau(B) = 2 \in \mathcal{F}_\tau$$

- **Set C :**

$$C = \{(S_\kappa, p_3)\}, \quad \tau(C) = 3 \in \mathcal{F}_\tau$$

- **Set D :**

$$D = \{(S_\kappa, p_1), (S_\kappa, p_2)\}, \quad \tau(D) = 2 \in \mathcal{F}_\tau$$

- **Set E :**

$$E = \{(S_\kappa, p_2), (S_\kappa, p_3)\}, \quad \tau(E) = 3 \in \mathcal{F}_\tau$$

- **Set F :**

$$F = \{(S_\kappa, p_1), (S_\kappa, p_2), (S_\kappa, p_3)\}, \quad \tau(F) = 3 \in \mathcal{F}_\tau$$

- **Set G :**

$$G = \emptyset, \quad \tau(G) = 4 \in \mathcal{F}_\tau$$

Evaluating Closure Under Finite Intersection. Intersecting B and C :

$$B = \{(S_\kappa, p_2)\}, \quad \tau(B) = 2$$

$$C = \{(S_\kappa, p_3)\}, \quad \tau(C) = 3$$

$$B \cap C = \emptyset, \quad \tau(B \cap C) = 4 \geq 2$$

Result: $B \cap C \in \mathcal{F}_\tau$.

Intersecting D and E :

$$D = \{(S_\kappa, p_1), (S_\kappa, p_2)\}, \quad \tau(D) = 2$$

$$E = \{(S_\kappa, p_2), (S_\kappa, p_3)\}, \quad \tau(E) = 3$$

$$D \cap E = \{(S_\kappa, p_2)\}, \quad \tau(D \cap E) = 2 \geq 2$$

Result: $D \cap E \in \mathcal{F}_\tau$.

Intersecting C and F :

$$C = \{(S_\kappa, p_3)\}, \quad \tau(C) = 3$$

$$F = \{(S_\kappa, p_1), (S_\kappa, p_2), (S_\kappa, p_3)\}, \quad \tau(F) = 3$$

$$C \cap F = \{(S_\kappa, p_3)\}, \quad \tau(C \cap F) = 3 \geq 2$$

Result: $C \cap F \in \mathcal{F}_\tau$.

Intersecting B and D :

$$B = \{(S_\kappa, p_2)\}, \quad \tau(B) = 2$$

$$D = \{(S_\kappa, p_1), (S_\kappa, p_2)\}, \quad \tau(D) = 2$$

$$B \cap D = \{(S_\kappa, p_2)\}, \quad \tau(B \cap D) = 2 \geq 2$$

Result: $B \cap D \in \mathcal{F}_\tau$.

Intersecting E and F :

$$E = \{(S_\kappa, p_2), (S_\kappa, p_3)\}, \quad \tau(E) = 3$$

$$F = \{(S_\kappa, p_1), (S_\kappa, p_2), (S_\kappa, p_3)\}, \quad \tau(F) = 3$$

$$E \cap F = \{(S_\kappa, p_2), (S_\kappa, p_3)\}, \quad \tau(E \cap F) = 3 \geq 2$$

Result: $E \cap F \in \mathcal{F}_\tau$.

Intersecting G with Any Set:

$$G = \emptyset, \quad \tau(G) = 4 \geq 2$$

$$G \cap A = \emptyset, \quad \tau(G \cap A) = 4 \geq 2$$

Result: $G \cap A \in \mathcal{F}_\tau$.

9.2. Summary of the Example. All intersections of the filtered sets satisfy the required properties of a filter.

9.2.1. Extending to an Ultrafilter.

Definition 9.1 (Provability Ultrafilter $\mathcal{U}_\tau$). An **ultrafilter** $\mathcal{U}_\tau$ extends the Provability Filter $\mathcal{F}_\tau$ to a maximal filter on X that contains $\mathcal{F}_\tau$. Formally, $\mathcal{U}_\tau$ satisfies:

$$\mathcal{F}_\tau \subseteq \mathcal{U}_\tau,$$

as a result for every subset $A \subseteq X$, either $A \in \mathcal{U}_\tau$ or $X \setminus A \in \mathcal{U}_\tau$, but not both.

Theorem 9.1 (Existence of an Ultrafilter). *Given a Provability Filter $\mathcal{F}_\tau$ on a set X , there exists an ultrafilter $\mathcal{U}_\tau$ such that $\mathcal{F}_\tau \subseteq \mathcal{U}_\tau$.*

Proof. By **Zorn's Lemma**, every partially ordered set in which every chain has an upper bound contains at least one maximal element. Consider the set of all filters on X that contain $\mathcal{F}_\tau$. This set is non-empty since $\mathcal{F}_\tau$ itself is a filter containing $\mathcal{F}_\tau$.

Partially order this set by subsetting ($\subseteq$). Let $\mathcal{C}$ be some chain (totally ordered subset) in this set. The **union** $\bigcup_{\mathcal{G} \in \mathcal{C}} \mathcal{G}$ serves as an upper bound for $\mathcal{C}$.

Filter Properties of the Union:

- **Non-Empty:** Since each $\mathcal{G} \in \mathcal{C}$ contains $\mathcal{F}_\tau$ and $X \in \mathcal{F}_\tau$, X is in the union.
- **Upward Closed:** If $A \in \bigcup \mathcal{C}$ and $A \subseteq B \subseteq X$, then $A \in \mathcal{G}$ for some $\mathcal{G} \in \mathcal{C}$. Since $\mathcal{G}$ is a filter, $B \in \mathcal{G} \subseteq \bigcup \mathcal{C}$.
- **Closed Under Finite Intersection:** If $A, B \in \bigcup \mathcal{C}$, then $A \in \mathcal{G}_1$ and $B \in \mathcal{G}_2$ for some $\mathcal{G}_1, \mathcal{G}_2 \in \mathcal{C}$. Since $\mathcal{C}$ is a chain, assume without a loss in generality that $\mathcal{G}_1 \subseteq \mathcal{G}_2$. Thus, $A, B \in \mathcal{G}_2$, and $A \cap B \in \mathcal{G}_2 \subseteq \bigcup \mathcal{C}$.

Therefore, $\bigcup \mathcal{C}$ is a filter containing $\mathcal{F}_\tau$, serving as an upper bound for $\mathcal{C}$.

Remark 9.1. By Zorn's Lemma, there exists a maximal filter $\mathcal{U}_\tau$ containing $\mathcal{F}_\tau$. This maximal filter becomes an **ultrafilter**, since no further subsets can be added without violating the filters properties. □

9.2.2. *Conclusion.* The Provability Filter $\mathcal{F}_\tau$ is a filter (monotonic by definition), and every chain of filters containing $\mathcal{F}_\tau$ has an upper bound within the set of these filters. Therefore, Zorn's Lemma guarantees the existence of a maximal filter $\mathcal{U}_\tau$, which as a result is an ultrafilter.

9.3. Handling Non-Measurable Cardinals.

Definition 9.2 (Non-Measurable Cardinal). A **Non-Measurable Cardinal** κ is a Large Cardinal that may exhibit self-embedding properties that render them **undefinable** within specific logical systems.

9.3.1. *Provability mass Function ζ .* To handle potential Non-Measurable Cardinals, the Provability Status Function τ can be a component to a mass function ζ that masses propositions based on their provability status within a logical system S_κ :

$$\zeta(S_\kappa, p_\alpha) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } p_\alpha \text{ is provable in } S_\kappa, \\ 2, & \text{if } \neg p_\alpha \text{ is provable in } S_\kappa, \\ 3, & \text{if } p_\alpha \text{ is undecidable in } S_\kappa, \\ 4, & \text{if } p_\alpha \text{ is undefinable in } S_\kappa. \end{cases}$$

The Provability mass Function τ for some given set of propositions $A \subseteq X$ is then defined as:

$$\zeta(A) = \sum_{(S_\kappa, p_\alpha) \in A} \tau(S_\kappa, p_\alpha)$$

Example 9.1 (Provability Status Function with a Non-Measurable Cardinal). Let κ be a **Non-Measurable Cardinal** and S_κ its associated logical system. Consider the set of propositions:

$$A = \{ (S_\kappa, p_\alpha) \mid \alpha < \lambda \},$$

where λ is some ordinal related to κ . Suppose that within S_κ :

- κ propositions are provable as true ($\tau = 1$),
- κ propositions are provable as false ($\tau = 2$),
- $\lambda - 2\kappa - \eta$ propositions are undecidable ($\tau = 3$),
- η propositions are undefinable ($\tau = 4$),

where η represents the number of undefinable propositions.

Then, the Total Mass of Provability $\zeta(A)$ is:

$$\zeta(A) = (\kappa \times 1) + (\kappa \times 2) + ((\lambda - 2\kappa - \eta) \times 3) + (\eta \times 4) = 3\lambda - 3\kappa + \eta.$$

This mass ensures that the presence of undefinable propositions are accounted for.

9.4. Transformation Property and Undefinable Propositions.

Theorem 9.2 (Consistency of ζ Under Transformation). *The Total Mass of Provability ζ remains consistent under the Transformation Property applied to logical systems for some S_κ associated with Non-Measurable Cardinals. For example for some universal embedding $e : V \rightarrow V$ which is an embedding with a critical point of κ , then for any $A \subseteq X$,*

$$\zeta(e(A)) = \zeta(A).$$

Note: This embedding reflects the entirety of space

Proof. Since e is an elementary embedding, it will preserve the provability status of propositions. Therefore, for each $(S_\kappa, p_\alpha) \in A$,

$$\tau(e(S_\kappa), e(p_\alpha)) = \tau(S_\kappa, p_\alpha).$$

Thus,

$$\zeta(e(A)) = \sum_{(e(S_\kappa), e(p_\alpha)) \in e(A)} \tau(e(S_\kappa), e(p_\alpha)) = \sum_{(S_\kappa, p_\alpha) \in A} \tau(S_\kappa, p_\alpha) = \zeta(A).$$

□

Remark 9.2. This theorem verifies that the Total Mass of Provability ζ is **invariant** under the Transformation Property, This invariance may be useful Non-Measurable Cardinals.

9.5. Illustrative Example. For intuition of the interaction between the Total Mass of Provability ζ , large cardinals, and cardinalities within the Observer Frame (OBF), consider the following example.

Example 9.2 (Provability Status Function with a Non-Measurable Cardinal). Let κ be some **Non-Measurable Cardinal** and S_κ its associated logical system. Consider the set of propositions:

$$A = \{ (S_\kappa, p_\alpha) \mid \alpha < \lambda \},$$

where λ is some ordinal related to κ . Then, suppose that within S_κ :

- κ propositions are provable as true ($\tau(S_\kappa, p_\alpha) = 1$),
- κ propositions are provable as false ($\tau(S_\kappa, p_\alpha) = 2$),
- $\lambda - 2\kappa - \eta$ propositions are undecidable ($\tau(S_\kappa, p_\alpha) = 3$),
- η propositions are undefinable ($\tau(S_\kappa, p_\alpha) = 4$),

where η represents the number of undefinable propositions.

Then, the **Total Mass of Provability** $\zeta(A)$ is calculated as:

$$\begin{aligned} \zeta(A) &= (\kappa \times 1) + (\kappa \times 2) + ((\lambda - 2\kappa - \eta) \times 3) + (\eta \times 4) = 3\lambda - 3\kappa + \eta. \\ \zeta(A) &= (\kappa \times 1) + (\kappa \times 2) + ((\lambda - 2\kappa - \eta) \times 3) + (\eta \times 4) \\ &= \kappa + 2\kappa + 3\lambda - 6\kappa - 3\eta + 4\eta \\ &= 3\lambda - 3\kappa + \eta. \end{aligned}$$

Given some **Transformation Property**, applying an elementary embedding $e : V \rightarrow V$ associated with the Non-Measurable Cardinal κ will not alter $\zeta(A)$:

$$\begin{aligned} \zeta(e(A)) &= \zeta(A) = 3\lambda - 3\kappa + \eta. \\ \zeta(e(A)) &= \sum_{(e(S_\kappa), e(p_\alpha)) \in e(A)} \tau(e(S_\kappa), e(p_\alpha)) \\ &= \sum_{(S_\kappa, p_\alpha) \in A} \tau(S_\kappa, p_\alpha) \\ &= \zeta(A). \end{aligned}$$

This demonstrates how the **Total Mass of Provability** ζ remains **invariant** within Non-Measurable Cardinals while maintaining its consistency.

10. LARGE OBSERVABLE CARDINALS: MEASURABLE CARDINALS

10.1. Definitions.

Definition 10.1 (Measurable Cardinal). A cardinal κ is called **measurable** if there exists a non-trivial, κ -complete ultrafilter U over κ . Equivalently, κ is measurable if there exists an elementary embedding function $r : V \rightarrow M$ with a critical point κ such that M is a transitive class containing all sequences of length less than κ from V .

Definition 10.2 (Ultrafilter). An **ultrafilter** U on a set X is a collection of subsets of X that satisfies:

- (1) $\emptyset \notin U$.
- (2) If $A \in U$ and $A \subseteq B \subseteq X$, then $B \in U$.
- (3) If $A, B \in U$, then $A \cap B \in U$.
- (4) For every subset $A \subseteq X$, either $A \in U$ or $X \setminus A \in U$, but not both.

10.2. Logical Spaces and Observers for Measurable Cardinals.

Definition 10.3 (Logical Space and Observer for Measurable Cardinals). For a measurable cardinal κ :

- **Logical Space** M_κ : Defined as the ultrapower $\text{Ult}(V, U)$, where U is a κ -complete ultrafilter on κ .
- **Observer** O_κ : An entity associated with M_κ that evaluates propositions within M_κ .

10.3. Construction of the Ultrapower Model.

Definition 10.4 (Ultrapower Construction). Given an elementary embedding $r : V \rightarrow M$ with critical point κ , the ultrapower $\text{Ult}(V, U)$ can be constructed using the ultrafilter U derived from r :

$$\text{Ult}(V, U) = \{[f]_U \mid f : \kappa \rightarrow V \text{ is a function}\}$$

where $[f]_U$ is the equivalence class of f under a ultrafilter U .

10.4. Proof of Existence of Measurable Cardinals within OBF.

Proof. Assumption: There exists a measurable cardinal κ within the Observer Frame(OBF).

Objective: To show that measurable cardinals exist within OBF and are appropriately modeled by Logical Spaces and Observers.

- (1) **Existence of Ultrafilter** U : By definition, since κ is measurable, there exists a non-trivial, κ -complete ultrafilter U on κ .
- (2) **Construction of Ultrapower** M_κ : Utilize the ultrafilter U to construct the ultrapower $M_\kappa = \text{Ult}(V, U)$.
- (3) **Elementary Embedding** r : The existence of U guarantees an elementary embedding $r : V \rightarrow M_\kappa$ with critical point κ , satisfying:

$$r(\kappa) > \kappa \quad \text{and} \quad V_\kappa \subseteq M_\kappa$$

- (4) **Association with Observer** O_κ : Observer O_κ is associated with M_κ , enabling it to evaluate propositions within the ultrapower M_κ .
- (5) **Observing OBF Axioms:**
 - **Axiom of Observer Existence:** O_κ exists for M_κ by definition.
 - **Axiom of the Reference Space:** Propositions evaluated within M_κ are uniquely handled by O_κ .
 - **Axiom of Observer Hierarchy Consistency:** Since r is elementary, O_κ can reflect properties from lower Observers O_α for $\alpha < \kappa$.
 - **Axiom of Non-Redundancy:** Each O_κ is uniquely associated with its respective M_κ , ensuring no duplication.
- (6) **Properties of Measurable Cardinals in OBF:**
 - **Reflection:** The elementary embedding r ensures that the properties of V up to κ are reflected in M_κ , allowing O_κ to evaluate a complex structure of propositions.
 - **Closure:** M_κ sequences of length less than κ , ensuring that O_κ can handle complex evaluations within its Logical Space.
- (7) **Conclusion:** The measurable cardinal κ within OBF is effectively modeled by the Logical Space M_κ and its associated Observer O_κ . The use of ultrafilters and elementary embedding functions ensures that OBF can represent

the properties of measurable cardinals while maintaining consistency with its axioms.

Therefore, measurable cardinals exist within OBF, The associated Logical Spaces and Observers are well-defined and consistent with OBF's axioms. $\square$

10.5. **Reasoning.** Measurable cardinals can introduce a higher level to the large cardinal hierarchy compared to Mahlo and Extendible cardinals.

10.6. Illustrative Example of Measurable Cardinal Embedding in OBF.

10.6.1. *Setup.* Let κ be a measurable cardinal within OBF, and let U be a κ -complete ultrafilter on κ . Consider the elementary embedding $r : V \rightarrow M_\kappa$ with critical point κ .

10.6.2. *Mapping Observers via r .* Define the mapping of Observers and Logical Spaces as follows:

Original Observer	Logical Space	Mapped Logical Space via r
O_1	M_1	$r(O_1) = O_1$
O_2	M_2	$r(O_2) = O_2$
$\vdots$	$\vdots$	$\vdots$
O_κ	M_κ	$r(O_\kappa) = O_{r(\kappa)}$
$O_{\kappa+1}$	$M_{\kappa+1}$	$r(O_{\kappa+1}) = O_{r(\kappa+1)}$

10.6.3. *Visualization of the Embedding.*

Observer	Logical Space	Mapping via r
O_1	M_1	$O_1 \mapsto O_1$
O_2	M_2	$O_2 \mapsto O_2$
$\vdots$	$\vdots$	$\vdots$
O_κ	M_κ	$O_\kappa \mapsto O_{r(\kappa)}$
$O_{\kappa+1}$	$M_{\kappa+1}$	$O_{\kappa+1} \mapsto O_{r(\kappa+1)}$

10.6.4. *Interpretation of $r(\kappa) > \lambda$ in the Measurable Cardinal Example.* In the context of measurable cardinals and elementary embeddings:

- **Critical Point:** κ is the smallest ordinal moved by r , i.e., $r(\kappa) > \kappa$.
- **Ordinal λ :** Choose $\lambda = \kappa + 1$.
- **Embedding Condition:** $r(\kappa) > \lambda$, which translates to $r(\kappa) > \kappa + 1$.

10.6.5. *Understanding $r(\kappa)(\lambda)$.* In this setting:

- $r(\kappa) = r(\kappa)$ (since r is an embedding).
- $r(\kappa)(\lambda) = r(\kappa + 1)$.

Therefore, $r(\kappa)(\lambda) = r(\kappa + 1)$, which ensures that the embedding maps $\kappa + 1$ into a higher ordinal, preserving the structure within M_κ .

11. ESTABLISHING ULTIMATE L: ALIGNING WITH ZFC AXIOMS

To construct and prove the existence of Ultimate L, This section will compare each of the ZFC axioms and analyze how the Observer axioms align with them to show the existence of Ultimate L. *OBF*

11.1. ZFC Axioms Overview. ZFC is a collection of axioms that form the majority of modern set theory. These axioms govern the behavior and properties of sets, ensuring consistency and preventing paradoxes such as Russell's Paradox. The necessary ZFC axioms needed to constructing Ultimate L include:

- (1) **Axiom of Extensionality**
- (2) **Axiom of Regularity**
- (3) **Axiom of Infinity**
- (4) **Axiom of Choice (AC)**

Each axiom forms the structural integrity and functional capabilities of OBF, therefore facilitating the construction of Ultimate L.

11.2. Axiom of Extensionality.

Definition 11.1 (Axiom of Extensionality). Two sets are equal if and only if they have the same elements. Formally,

$$\forall A, B (A = B \leftrightarrow \forall x (x \in A \leftrightarrow x \in B))$$

Significance for Ultimate L Construction: The Axiom of Extensionality states that sets are uniquely determined by their elements. In context of Ultimate L, this axiom ensures that both logical spaces and observers are precisely defined by their constituent elements. This is essential maintaining consistency and avoiding ambiguities in the model's structure.

11.3. Axiom of Regularity.

Definition 11.2 (Axiom of Regularity). Every non-empty set A contains an element that is disjoint from A . Formally,

$$\forall A (A \neq \emptyset \rightarrow \exists x (x \in A \wedge x \cap A = \emptyset))$$

Significance for Ultimate L Construction: The Axiom of Regularity removes the possibility of sets containing themselves, directly or indirectly, as a result it prevents paradoxes from occurring. For Ultimate L, this axiom ensures a well-founded hierarchical structure of sets, ensuring organized logical spaces and observers without encountering cyclical dependencies.

11.4. Axiom of Infinity.

Definition 11.3 (Axiom of Infinity). There exists a set that contains the empty set and is closed under the operation of forming the successor set. Formally,

$$\exists A (\emptyset \in A \wedge \forall x (x \in A \rightarrow x \cup \{x\} \in A))$$

Significance for Ultimate L Construction: The Axiom of Infinity is useful when discussing infinite sets and large cardinals, which are inherent within the Observer Frame. Ultimate relies on the existence of infinite hierarchies and the existence of large cardinals in. This axiom ensures that the model can contain the infinite constructs required for Ultimate L's functionality.

11.5. Axiom of Choice (AC).

Definition 11.4 (Axiom of Choice). Given any collection of non-empty sets, there exists a choice function that selects exactly one element from each set. Formally,

$$\forall \mathcal{F} (\mathcal{F} \neq \emptyset \wedge \forall A \in \mathcal{F} (A \neq \emptyset) \rightarrow \exists f (f : \mathcal{F} \rightarrow \bigcup \mathcal{F} \wedge \forall A \in \mathcal{F} (f(A) \in A)))$$

Significance for Ultimate L Construction: The Axiom of Choice (AC) maintains needed aspects involving cardinality, product sets, and the existence of certain types of bases. Within the Observer Frame, The AC makes it possible to select and organize elements across various logical spaces and observers. For Ultimate L, AC ensures that the model can handle arbitrary selections and construction.

11.6. Alignment of OBF with ZFC Axioms. To formally prove the existence of Ultimate L within the Observer Frame, the frame must adhere to each of the previously mentioned ZFC axioms. Below is an analysis of how the Observer Frame (OBF) aligns with these axioms:

11.6.1. *Compliance with the Axiom of Extensionality.* - **Logical Spaces Definition:** Each Logical Space M_n within $\mathcal{M}$ is uniquely determined by its elements, ensuring that no two distinct Logical Spaces have identical memberships.

- **Observers' Evaluation:** Observers O_n evaluate propositions based solely on the elements within their associated Logical Spaces, maintaining the principle that sets (Logical Spaces) are defined by their elements.

11.6.2. *Compliance with the Axiom of Regularity.* - **Hierarchy Structure:** The OBF enforces a well-founded hierarchy where each Logical Space has observers evaluating sets disjoint from themselves, preventing self-referential or cyclical evaluations.

- **Non-Empty Logical Spaces:** Every non-empty Logical Space contains observers that evaluate propositions disjoint from their own evaluations, aligning with the Regularity axiom's requirement.

11.6.3. *Compliance with the Axiom of Infinity.* - **Infinite Logical Spaces:** OBF incorporates infinite sequences of Logical Spaces $\mathcal{M} = \{M_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{K}}$, ensuring the existence of an infinite hierarchy necessary for discussing large cardinals.

- **Large Cardinals Integration:** Infinite Logical Spaces embed large cardinals, which are necessary to Ultimate L's construction.

11.6.4. *Compliance with the Axiom of Choice (AC).* - **Selection of Observers:** OBF uses AC inherently by allowing the selection of observers O_n from the Observer Set $\mathcal{O}$, ensuring that some choice function exists for selecting specific observers across Logical Spaces.

- **Handling Cardinalities:** AC enables OBF to manage and manipulate different cardinalities within various Logical Spaces.

12. ESTABLISHING ULTIMATE L: EXISTENCE WITHIN OBF

12.1. Introduction. The construction of **Ultimate L** within the **Observer Frame (OBF)** requires a rigorous verification that OBF adheres to all axioms of **Zermelo-Fraenkel set theory with the Axiom of Choice (ZFC)**. To construct this, A **Proof by Comparison** strategy, comparing OBF with standard ZFC models.

This approach ensures that every axiom is satisfied within OBF, confirming the viability of constructing Ultimate L.

12.2. Overview of OBF. The OBF is structured around two primary components:

- **Logical Spaces ($\mathcal{M}$):** A collection of mathematical spaces M_n associated with Observers.
- **Observers ($\mathcal{O}$):** Entities O_n that evaluate propositions within their respective Logical Spaces.

In addition, OBF incorporates Ultrafilters and Elementary Embeddings to make it easier to map Observers onto Logical Spaces, in order to integrate large cardinals in order to construct Ultimate L.

12.3. Finite and Infinite Cardinal Examples. To comprehend OBF's compatibility with ZFC axioms, we first observed:

- **Finite Mapping Example:** Demonstrated how Observers and Logical Spaces interact within a finite sequence, showing the concept of a critical point.
- **Infinite Cardinal Example Using δ :** Extended the finite analogy to an infinite setting, incorporating measurable cardinals and ultrapowers to reflect the properties required for large cardinals.

These examples serve as an illustrations of OBF's mechanisms, setting the groundwork for a formal proof of its compliance with ZFC axioms.

12.4. Proof by Comparison Strategy. The **Proof by Comparison** will use the following steps:

- (1) **Identify comparisons:** Compare between elements of OBF and components of standard ZFC models.
- (2) **Verify Axiom Compliance:** Demonstrate that each ZFC axiom holds within OBF by using the established parallels .
- (3) **Conclude Model Equivalence:** confirm that, through these comparisons, OBF satisfies all ZFC axioms, therefore enabling the construction of Ultimate L.

12.5. Verification of ZFC Axioms in OBF. Verification of Necessary ZFC axioms within OBF.

12.5.1. *Axiom of Extensionality.*

Definition 12.1 (Axiom of Extensionality). Two sets are equal if and only if they have the same elements. Formally,

$$\forall A, B (A = B \leftrightarrow \forall x (x \in A \leftrightarrow x \in B))$$

Verification:

In OBF:

- **Logical Spaces Uniqueness:** Each Logical Space M_n is uniquely determined by its elements, ensuring that no two distinct Logical Spaces have identical memberships.
- **Observer Evaluation:** Observers O_n evaluate propositions based solely on the elements within their associated Logical Spaces M_n , maintaining the principle that sets are defined by their elements.

Thus, the Axiom of Extensionality is satisfied as OBF ensures set equality through identical element memberships.

12.5.2. *Axiom of Regularity.*

Definition 12.2 (Axiom of Regularity). Every non-empty set A contains an element that is disjoint from A . Formally,

$$\forall A (A \neq \emptyset \rightarrow \exists x (x \in A \wedge x \cap A = \emptyset))$$

Verification:

In OBF:

- **Hierarchical Structure:** OBF enforces a well-founded hierarchy where each Logical Space M_n has Observers evaluating sets disjoint from themselves, preventing self-referential or cyclical dependencies.
- **Disjoint Evaluation:** For any non-empty Logical Space M_n , there exists an Observer O_m such that O_m evaluates propositions in a Logical Space M_m where $M_m \cap M_n = \emptyset$.

This structure ensures that every non-empty set (Logical Space) contains an element (Observer's evaluation space) disjoint from it, therefore satisfying the Axiom of Regularity.

12.5.3. *Axiom of Infinity.*

Definition 12.3 (Axiom of Infinity). There exists a set that contains the empty set and is closed under the operation of forming the successor set. Formally,

$$\exists A (\emptyset \in A \wedge \forall x (x \in A \rightarrow x \cup \{x\} \in A))$$

Verification:

In OBF:

- **Infinite Logical Spaces:** OBF inherently includes infinite sequences of Logical Spaces $\mathcal{M} = \{M_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$, ensuring the existence of an infinite hierarchy needed for discussing large cardinals.
- **Successor Operations:** Each Logical Space M_{n+1} is constructed as a successor to M_n , similar to forming successor sets in the Axiom of Infinity.

By maintaining an infinite sequence of logically structured spaces, OBF satisfies the Axiom of Infinity, facilitating the inclusion of infinite sets and large cardinals essential for Ultimate L.

12.5.4. *Axiom of Choice (AC).*

Definition 12.4 (Axiom of Choice). Given any collection of non-empty sets, there exists a choice function that selects exactly one element from each set. Formally,

$$\forall \mathcal{F} (\mathcal{F} \neq \emptyset \wedge \forall A \in \mathcal{F} (A \neq \emptyset) \rightarrow \exists f (f : \mathcal{F} \rightarrow \bigcup \mathcal{F} \wedge \forall A \in \mathcal{F} (f(A) \in A)))$$

Verification:

In OBF:

- **Selection of Observers:** OBF uses the Axiom of Choice implicitly by allowing the selection of Observers O_n from the Observer Set $\mathcal{O}$, ensuring that a choice function exists for selecting specific Observers across Logical Spaces.

- **Handling Cardinalities:** AC enables OBF to manage and manipulate different cardinalities within various Logical Spaces.

By including the selection processes and managing cardinalities through using or not using the AC, OBF aligns with AC.

12.6. Verification of Remaining ZFC Axioms in the Observer Framework.

12.6.1. Axiom of Pairing.

Definition 12.5 (Axiom of Pairing). For any two sets A and B , there exists a set that contains exactly A and B . Formally,

$$\forall A, B \exists C \forall x (x \in C \leftrightarrow x = A \vee x = B)$$

Verification within OBF:

- **Existence of Observers for Logical Spaces:** By **Axiom 2.1**, for any Logical Spaces M_n and M_m corresponding to sets A and B , there exist Observers O_n and O_m that evaluate propositions within these spaces.
- **Axiom of the Reference Space (2.2):** For any pair of sets A and B , there exist unique Logical Spaces M_n and M_m such that $\mathcal{E}(S_n, M_n) = \text{True}$ and $\mathcal{E}(S_m, M_m) = \text{True}$.
- **Axiom of Comprehensive Coverage (2.6):** For all possible propositions, even including those asserting the existence of the paired set $C = \{A, B\}$, there exist an overset evaluation covered by the collective evaluations of Observers.
- **Logical Space Alternation (2.8):** The construction of the paired set C in a specific Logical Space M_k , where k corresponds to the next logical space in the alternating sequence.
- **Construction Mechanism:** This allows for the creation of a new Logical Space M_k where the paired set C is evaluated as:

$$\mathcal{E}(C, M_k) = \mathcal{E}_{\text{pair}}(A, B) = \{A, B\}$$

- **Uniqueness and Non-Redundancy (2.4):** The set $C = \{A, B\}$ is uniquely associated with Logical Space M_k , preventing redundancy and maintaining the integrity of set constructions.

Therefore, the Observer Frame (OBF) satisfies the Axiom of Pairing by ensuring that for any two sets A and B , a unique set $C = \{A, B\}$ exists within a Logical Space, adhering to OBF Axioms.

12.6.2. Axiom of Union.

Definition 12.6 (Axiom of Union). For any set A , there exists a set that the elements of the elements of A . Formally,

$$\forall A \exists B \forall x (x \in B \leftrightarrow \exists C (C \in A \wedge x \in C))$$

Verification within OBF:

- **Logical Spaces Representation:** Consider a set A represented by a Logical Space M_n . Each element $C \in A$ is associated with its own Logical Space M_m .
- **Axiom of Observer Existence (2.1):** For each $C \in A$, there exists an Observer O_m that evaluates propositions within M_m .

- **Axiom of Comprehensive Coverage (2.6):** Ensures that all elements $x \in C$ for every $C \in A$ are evaluated and included in the union set B .
- **Axiom of Logical Space (2.8):** Makes it possible to create a new Logical Space M_k where the union set B is evaluated as:

$$\mathcal{E}(B, M_k) = \bigcup_{C \in A} C$$

- **Axiom of Non-Redundancy (2.4):** The union set B is uniquely associated with Logical Space M_k , preventing duplication.
- **Axiom of Referential Consistency (2.5):** The evaluation of the union respects the ordering and independence of evaluations across different Logical Spaces.

Therefore, the OBF satisfies the Axiom of Union by systematically collecting approaching elements from the subsets of A into a unified set B within a designated Logical Space.

12.6.3. Axiom of Power Set.

Definition 12.7 (Axiom of Power Set). For any set A , there exists a set $P(A)$ that the subsets of A . Formally,

$$\forall A \exists B \forall C (C \in B \leftrightarrow C \subseteq A)$$

Verification within OBF:

- **Logical Spaces for Subsets:** Given a set A represented by Logical Space M_n , each subset $C \subseteq A$ corresponds to a distinct Logical Space M_m .
- **Axiom of Observer Existence (2.1):** For every subset $C \subseteq A$, there exists an Observer O_m that evaluates propositions within M_m .
- **Axiom of Comprehensive Coverage (2.6):** Ensures that all possible subsets $C \subseteq A$ are evaluated and included in the Power Set $P(A)$.
- **Axiom of Logical Space (2.8):** Makes it possible to create a Logical Space M_k where the Power Set $P(A)$ is evaluated as:

$$\mathcal{E}(P(A), M_k) = \mathcal{P}(A)$$

where $\mathcal{P}(A)$ denotes the Power Set of A .

- **Axiom of Non-Redundancy (2.4):** Each subset $C \subseteq A$ is uniquely associated with its Logical Space M_m , ensuring the uniqueness of elements within $P(A)$.
- **Axiom of Referential Consistency (2.5):** Maintains the evaluation of subsets occurs in a consistent and orderly manner across different Logical Spaces, preserving the integrity of the Power Set construction.

Therefore, OBF satisfies the Axiom of Power Set by carefully generating and evaluating all possible subsets of a given set A , thereby constructing the Power Set $P(A)$ within a dedicated Logical Space.

12.6.4. Axiom of Replacement.

Definition 12.8 (Axiom of Replacement). If F is a definable function and A is a set, then the image of A under F is also a set. Formally,

$$\forall A, F (\text{Function}(F) \wedge \forall x \in A F(x) \text{ is defined}) \rightarrow \exists B \forall y (y \in B \leftrightarrow \exists x \in A (y = F(x)))$$

Verification within OBF:

- **Definable Functions within Logical Spaces:** Consider a definable function F within Logical Space M_n . Each application $F(x)$ for $x \in A$ corresponds to a unique evaluation within a designated Logical Space M_m .
- **Axiom of Observer Existence (2.1):** For every element $x \in A$, there exists an Observer O_m that evaluates $F(x)$ within Logical Space M_m .
- **Axiom of Comprehensive Coverage (2.6):** All images $F(x)$ for $x \in A$ are covered by the collective evaluations of Observers, through the existence of the set $B = \{F(x) \mid x \in A\}$.
- **Axiom of Logical Space (2.8):** Makes it possible if necessary and crossing logical spaces to construct a new Logical Space M_k where the image set B is evaluated as:

$$\mathcal{E}(B, M_k) = \{F(x) \mid x \in A\}$$

- **Axiom of Non-Redundancy (2.4):** Each image $F(x)$ is uniquely associated within its Logical Space M_m , ensuring the uniqueness of elements within B .
- **Axiom of Referential Consistency (2.5):** The evaluation of $F(x)$ respects the logical ordering and independence across different Logical Spaces, therefore maintaining the integrity of the Replacement process.

Therefore, OBF satisfies the Axiom of Replacement by ensuring that the image of any set under a definable function is evaluated and contained within a newly constructed Logical Space if necessary, thereby maintaining the closure properties required by ZFC.

12.6.5. Axiom of Separation (Subset Axiom).

Definition 12.9 (Axiom of Separation). For any set A and any definable property $\phi(x)$, there exists a subset of A containing exactly those elements x in A that satisfy $\phi(x)$. Formally,

$$\forall A, \phi \exists B \forall x (x \in B \leftrightarrow (x \in A \wedge \phi(x)))$$

Verification within OBF:

- **Definable Properties within Logical Spaces:** Given some set A represented by Logical Space M_n and a definable property $\phi(x)$, the subset $B = \{x \in A \mid \phi(x)\}$ corresponds to evaluations within Logical Space M_m .
- **Axiom of Observer Existence (2.1):** For each element $x \in A$, there exists an Observer O_m that evaluates whether x satisfies the property $\phi(x)$ within M_m .
- **Axiom of Comprehensive Coverage (2.6):** All evaluations of $\phi(x)$ for $x \in A$ are covered by the Observers, enforcing the existence of the subset B .
- **Axiom of Logical Space (2.8):** Makes it possible to construct of a new Logical Space M_k where the subset B is evaluated as:

$$\mathcal{E}(B, M_k) = \{x \in A \mid \phi(x)\}$$

- **Axiom of Non-Redundancy (2.4):** Each element x in the subset B is uniquely associated within its Logical Space M_m , ensuring the uniqueness of elements within B .

- **Axiom of Referential Consistency (2.5):** The evaluation of $\phi(x)$ respects the logical ordering and independence across different Logical Spaces, preserving the integrity of the Separation process.

Therefore, OBF satisfies the Axiom of Separation by making it possible form subsets based on definable properties within designated Logical Spaces, thereby ensuring precise and well-defined subset constructions in accordance with ZFC.

12.7. Summary of ZFC Axioms Verification. By verifying OBF to each ZFC axiom—Infinity, Regularity, Extentionality, Pairing, Union, Power Set, Replacement, Choice, and Separation— It is shown that OBF aligns with and satisfies the principles of Zermelo-Fraenkel set theory with and without the Axiom of Choice. By using each OBF axioms such as Observer Existence, Reference Space, Observer Hierarchy Consistency, Non-Redundancy, Referential Consistency, Comprehensive Coverage, and Logical Space Alternation, OBF ensures that all necessary set-theoretic constructions and operations are supported within itself. This allows for the analyzation of a Ultimate L, while maintaining consistency and integrity within set theories established axioms.

12.8. Constructing Ultimate L within OBF. By verifying OBF satisfies all ZFC axioms, we can form an outline of the construction of Ultimate L within ZFC and OBF.

12.8.1. Integration of Large Cardinals. Incorporate large cardinals, such as **measurable** and **extendible cardinals** within Ultimate L. Within OBF:

- **Ultrafilters and Embeddings:** OBF utilizes ultrafilters and elementary embeddings to map Observers onto Logical Spaces, making it possible for the reflection and extension properties for large cardinals to function.
- **Critical Points:** Critical points in embedding functions serve as hinge points, ensuring that large cardinals like δ (as shown in the infinite cardinal example) are appropriately integrated in the model.

12.8.2. Formation of Ultimate L. Ultimate L is constructed as the combination of these integrated structures:

- (1) **Definable Inner Model:** Ultimate L is defined as the most extensive inner model within OBF that incorporates all large cardinals while maintaining its definability and structural coherence.
- (2) **Consistency with ZFC:** Through the verified compliance within ZFC axioms, Ultimate L inherits properties required for a consistent and robust set-theoretic model.
- (3) **Representation:** Ultimate L serves as an inner model, containing the entirety of OBF's Logical Spaces and Observers in a manner that reflects the universe V up to large cardinals.

12.8.3. Proof of Ultimate L's Existence.

Theorem 12.1 (Existence of Ultimate L). *Within OBF, there exists an inner model, denoted as Ultimate L, that satisfies all OBF/ZFC axioms and incorporates all large cardinals present in OBF.*

Proof. To show the existence of Ultimate L within OBF, we verified that OBF satisfies all Zermelo-Fraenkel set theory axioms with the Axiom of Choice (ZFC) and can effectively integrate large cardinals, through its structural components. The proof proceeds through the following key steps:

- (1) **Compliance with ZFC Axioms:** In Section 12.5, OBF has been verified against all ZFC axioms, including both the necessary axioms (Extensionality, Regularity, Infinity, and Choice) and additional axioms (Pairing, Union, Power Set, Replacement, and Separation). Each axiom has been verified to hold within OBF against its the properties and axioms, such as Observer Existence, Reference Space, Observer Hierarchy Consistency, Non-Redundancy, Referential Consistency, Comprehensive Coverage.
- (2) **Incorporation of Large Cardinals:** OBF employs ultrafilters and elementary embedding functions, to integrating large cardinals, into OBF. For every $\lambda > \delta$, there exists a normal fine ultrafilter $\mathcal{U}$ on $\mathcal{P}_\delta(\lambda)$ within OBF, satisfying:

$$\mathcal{U} = \{A \subseteq \mathcal{P}_\delta(\lambda) \mid r''\lambda \in r(A)\}$$

where $r : V \rightarrow M$ is the ultrapower embedding generated by $\mathcal{U}$. This ultrafilter $\mathcal{U}$ is fine and normal, ensuring that δ is supercompact within both V and the inner model $N \subseteq V$.

Additionally, models for supercompactness, as defined by weak extender models. A weak extender model $N \subseteq V$ for " δ is supercompact" ensures that for all $\lambda > \delta$, there exists a normal fine ultrafilter $\mathcal{U}$ on $\mathcal{P}_\delta(\lambda)$ such that:

$$\mathcal{P}_\delta(\lambda) \cap N \in \mathcal{U} \quad \text{and} \quad \mathcal{U} \cap N \in N.$$

This inclusion of δ 's supercompactness in N with its supercompactness in V maintains the integrity of large cardinals within a Ultimate L.

- (3) **Definability and Structural Coherence:** Ultimate L is constructed as a definable inner model within OBF, ensuring that it maintains a coherent and consistent structure in alignment along with ZFC. The definability of Ultimate L is preserved and essential properties such as well-foundedness and closure under standard set operations are maintained. This Ultimate L can function as a comprehensive model that contains the entirety of OBF's Logical Spaces and Observers.
- (4) **Universality and Rigidity of Ultimate L:** The **Universality Theorem** within OBF states that any elementary embedding $\pi : N \cap V_{\gamma+1} \rightarrow N \cap V_{\pi(\gamma)+1}$ with critical point $\geq \delta$ must reside within N . This implies that Ultimate L, as an inner model N , cannot admit non-trivial elementary embeddings, thereby enforcing its **rigidity**.

Results of Rigidity:

- **Consistency with ZFC and Supercompactness:** Rigidity makes it possible for Ultimate L to uphold its consistency with the ZFC axioms while accurately reflecting the supercompactness of δ .
 - **Stability of the Model:** Rigidity contributes to the overall stability of Ultimate L, ensuring that it remains a fixed and unalterable structure within OBF, free from **internal shifts** that could disrupt its alignment with ZFC.
- (5) **Existence via Proof by Comparison:** By Proof by Comparison strategy "Similar to construction", and by verifying OBF with standard ZFC models

and ensuring that all ZFC axioms will hold within OBF: An analysis is confirms that Ultimate L exists as a model within OBF that adheres to ZFC while maintaining its structural integrity. The axioms provided by OBF ensures that Ultimate L oversets all necessary set-theoretic constructs, therefore validating its existence and consistency.

- (6) **Construction of Ultimate L:** Given that OBF satisfies all ZFC axioms, standard inner model techniques within OBF can be used to construct Ultimate L. OBF axioms ensure that all required set operations and constructions are permitted, thus, allowing for the systematic building of Ultimate L as an inner model. The properties of OBF enforces that the definition and expansion of Ultimate L to include all necessary sets and structures.

Conclusion: By verifying that OBF satisfies all ZFC axioms, effectively integrates large cardinals, and maintaining definability and structural coherence, we have confirmed the existence of Ultimate L within OBF. □

13. RESULTS

- **Strengthening OBF:** By integrating both measurable and non-measurable cardinals, OBF's utility is markedly expanded. As a result of the Inclusion of larger cardinals.
- **Addressing Unresolved Problems:** OBF can now potentially contribute to resolving significant open questions in set theory, such as the Continuum Hypothesis. by means of an expanded analysis

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